

Evaluation Criteria for Model-driven Engineering Solutions

Adel Vahdati, Raman Ramsin

Department of Computer Engineering, Sharif University of Technology Azadi Avenue, Tehran, Iran
adel.vahdati97@sharif.edu , ramsin@sharif.edu

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This document is supplementary material accompanying the paper titled "Microservice-based model-driven architecture for implementing modeling and model-transformation as a service". This document examines the criteria used to evaluate Model-driven Engineering (MDE) solutions. It presents the results of a survey assessing factors such as scalability, reusability, collaboration, usability, and flexibility in relation to MDDPlatform. The survey provides empirical insights into the effectiveness and practicality of MDE methods and tools.

1. Criteria for Evaluating MDE Solutions

A survey study was conducted to investigate the evaluation methods of MDE solutions and the criteria and metrics used to evaluate the relevant quality attributes, especially scalability, reusability, and collaboration. Four research questions were formulated to guide the study, including: 1) how the proposed solutions related to MDE and software modeling are evaluated (RQ1), and 2) how scalability, reusability, and collaboration are evaluated in MDE approaches (RQ2, RQ3, RQ4). The following search query was used to search databases for relevant articles: (“MDD” OR “MDE” OR “Model-driven development” OR “Model-driven engineering”) AND (“Reusability” OR “Scalability” OR “Collaboration” OR “Collaborative”) AND (“Modeling” OR “Model”). Then, a set of criteria were defined to filter out irrelevant articles. In the first stage of filtering, papers not related to MDE were removed based on the titles and abstracts. In the second stage, the remaining papers were studied to identify those related to the four research questions. Data summarization, aggregation, and analysis were then performed to answer the research questions.

1.1. Answer to RQ1

The evaluation methods used in MDD and MDE solutions can be categorized into four main groups: university case studies, industrial case studies, user studies, and comparative analysis (Shamsujjoha et al., 2021). University case studies involve creating an initial version of an application or implementing certain components on a specific platform to evaluate the solution. Qualitative criteria, user studies or industry-standard practices may be employed to assess the results (Shamsujjoha et al., 2021). Industrial case studies, on the other hand, involve creating a real version of the application as a pilot project and comparing the results with common industrial samples. Use case examples can also be defined to evaluate the impact of the solution on qualitative attributes (Shamsujjoha et al., 2021). User studies involve gathering participants' perspectives through interviews, surveys, and analysis of the collected information (Shamsujjoha et al., 2021). Comparative analysis involves creating an application or component and comparing it with other approaches (Shamsujjoha et al., 2021).

1.2. Answer to RQ2

We examined several research studies (Akiki & Maalouf, 2021; Bagherzadeh et al., 2021; Bruneliere et al., 2020; Bucchiarone et al., 2020; Daniel et al., 2019; David et al., 2023; Gómez et al., 2020; Ivanchikj et al., 2022; Jahed et al., 2021; D. Kolovos et al., 2013; D. S. Kolovos et al., 2015; López & Cuadrado, 2022; Mkaouar et al., 2023; Ogunyomi et al., 2019; Rocco et al., 2015; Tröls et al., 2022), and identified the features and requirements that are necessary to improve scalability. We also identified various quantitative and qualitative criteria for evaluating scalability. These requirements and the corresponding criteria are presented in Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3.

Table 1: Requirements and features that are necessary to fulfil scalability

Requirements & Features	Details
Support for systematic creation of large-scale models	It should be possible to define domain specific languages
	It should be possible to model the scope of the problem from different perspectives
	It should be possible to systematically manage the models resulting from the description of the problem from various perspectives.
Support for systematic development of domain-specific languages	It should be possible to define the constituent concepts of a language.
	It should be possible to determine the characteristics of a concept and its relationship with other concepts that make up the language.
Support for interaction and collaboration of large teams of designers	The model changes resulting from team member collaboration and participation should be published online.
	It should be possible to decompose the problem domain into subdomains and assign each subdomain to a group of designers.
	There should be systematic management of the problem domain, its subdomains, and the models describing each subdomain.
Support for large-scale models transformation	It should be possible to perform transformations on large models incrementally.
	It should be possible to define fine-grained transformations, each of which is performed on a small part of the model.
	It should be possible to define and execute a chain of transformations on large models.
	It should be possible to perform transformations on large models without the need to fully load that model.
Support for storing, indexing, and retrieving the models efficiently	Storage should be done in such a way that it is possible to search among the elements of a model.
	It should be possible to retrieve some elements of a model without having to load other elements.
Support for the large model decomposition into the different parts	The platform should support the large model decomposition into different parts, and build and compose them again.
Support for merging different models and creating a large model	It should be possible to merge the data of several models with the same metamodel in the form of a larger model with the similar metamodel.
	It should be possible to merge the data of several models with various metamodels in the form of an output model whose metamodel is a superset of input metamodels.
Providing a simple view of models	Models should be organized in the form of a hierarchical structure of concepts and domain objects.
	It should be possible to display the details of each element according to the user's request.
Organizing the models at different levels of abstraction	It should be possible to decompose the problem domain into the subdomains and describe them from different perspectives.
	It should be possible to describe and manage models at different abstraction levels of CIM, PIM, and PSM.
Support for querying the large-scale models	The platform should support querying the large-scale models.
Support for cloud-based storage and remote access to the artifacts via the internet	The platform should support cloud-based storage and remote access to the artifacts via the internet.
Access to specific model elements with support for lazy loading as needed	It should be possible to access and display parts of a model, without the need to load it completely.
	It should be possible to load the elements of a model, as needed or based on the user's request.
Support for parallelization and concurrent execution of transformations	The platform should support parallelization and concurrent execution of transformations to improve performance.
Support for iterative incremental transformations	The platform should support iterative incremental transformations, and maintain the source and target models in sync.
Support for complexity management by defining the process of model-driven development	It should be possible to define and configure the MDD processes.
	It should be possible to run the MDD process and perform transformations in an automatic or semi-automatic way.

Table 2: Qualitative criteria for evaluating the scalability quality attribute

Domain	Criteria
Model Transformation	The ability to transform large-scale models
	The ability to execute transformation concurrently
	The ability to perform transformations in iterative incremental fashion
	The ability to maintain the source and target models in sync
	The ability to perform lazy computation
	The accuracy of the transformed models
Tools & Modeling Approaches	The ability to create models in a systematic manner
	The ease of creating large-scale models
	The accuracy of the created models
	The ability to develop languages in a systematic manner
	The ease of developing domain-specific languages
	The accuracy of the developed languages
	The ability to query large-scale models
	The ease of querying large-scale models
	The accuracy of the query results
	The ability to explore and discover models in a systematic manner
	The ability to store, index, and retrieve models efficiently
	The accuracy of the stored models
	The ability to access artifacts stored remotely
	The ease of accessing artifacts remotely
	The ability to decompose models
	The ease of decomposing models
	The accuracy of the decomposed models
	The ability to merge models
	The ease of merging models
	The accuracy of the merged models
	The ability to load model elements using lazy loading
	The ability to access specific model elements without loading entire model
	The ability to visualize models and traverse between model elements
	The ease of visualizing and traversing models
	The accuracy of the visualized models
	The ability to organize models at the different levels of abstraction
	The ease of viewing models at the different levels of abstraction
	The ability to organize model elements in a hierarchical structure
	The ease of navigating the hierarchical structure of the model elements
	The accuracy of the hierarchical structure of the model elements
MDE Process	The ability to create and refine models through collaboration of large teams of designers
	The ease of creating and refining models through collaboration of large teams of designers
	The ability to define the MDD process
	The ability to manage complexity in a systematic manner
	The ease of configuring and running the MDD processes

Table 3: Quantitative criteria for evaluating the scalability quality attribute

Domain	Criteria	Influential variables
Model Transformation	Transformation execution time	Structural complexity of the models; Size of the models; Number of elements in models; Complexity of transformation rules; The number of processors
	Memory consumption	
	Resource consumption	
	The number of transformations that can be executed concurrently	
Tools & Modeling Approaches	Model loading time	Structural complexity of the models; Size of the model; Number of elements in the models
	Model storage time	
	Model updating time	
	Time required for the change propagation	
	Time required for model comparison	
	Time required for model querying	
	Time required for model traversal	
	Maximum displayable elements of a model	
	Memory consumption	
	Resource consumption	
	Network resource consumption	
Computational complexity		
MDE Process	Number of concurrent users in the modeling process	Geographical distribution of team members
	Time required for receiving the change notifications in the collaborative modeling.	

1.3. Answer to RQ3

After reviewing several studies (Alam et al., 2018; Chavarriaga et al., 2014; Cuadrado et al., 2014; Franzago et al., 2018; Kusel et al., 2015; Panahandeh et al., 2021; Wagelaar et al., 2011; Wimmer et al., 2010), we identified several requirements and features that are necessary to support reusability. Additionally, we identified a set of qualitative and quantitative criteria and metrics related to reusability that can be used to assess this quality attribute. Table 4 and Table 5 present these requirements and the corresponding criteria for evaluating reusability.

Table 4: Requirements and features that are needed to support reusability

Requirements & Features	Details
Support for defining modular model transformations	It should be possible to define fine-grained transformations
	It should be possible to define a chain of transformations and run this chain automatically or semi-automatically.
Support for reusing the existing transformations	The platform should support reusing the existing transformations.
Support for composing transformations and creating a chain of transformations	The platform should support composing the existing transformations and creating a chain of transformations.
Support for reusing existing models	It should be possible to use the elements defined in a domain model to create a model with a similar metamodel, but not necessarily in the same domain.
	It should be possible to automatically use part of the model elements to create a model with a different metamodel.
Support for reusing existing metamodels	It should be possible to query and view the existing modeling languages (metamodels) and their constituent elements.
	It should be possible to reuse the constituent concepts of a metamodel to define a new metamodel.
Support for the abstract mechanisms for applying transformations to a variety of metamodels	Dependencies between the transformation and their input and output metamodels should be loosely defined.
	It should be possible to define a transformations in the form of transformation model.
	Model transformations must be configurable to conform to different metamodels.

Requirements & Features	Details
	Model transformations must be defined in the form of the template or pattern that can be used for the family of metamodels.
Support for tailoring model transformations to a specific metamodel	Transformations should be parametric and configurable at run time.
	To define a transformation, the transformation model approach or higher-order transformations can be used so that these transformations can be transformed into the desired transformations, suitable for a specific metamodel.
Support for reusing the existing MDD processes	It should be possible to define and query the existing MDD processes.
	It should be possible to configure the existing MDD process according to the new problem domain.
Support for the well-defined interfaces to describe and retrieve model elements	The necessary APIs for creating, querying and retrieving model elements must be defined.
	It should be possible to access the elements remotely by calling the web API
Support for discovering artifacts created through collaboration during different phases	It should be possible to query among the existing models based on the metamodel
	It should be possible to query among existing models based on the domain and abstraction levels of CIM, PIM and PSM.
	It should be possible to query transformations based on input and output metamodels.
	It should be possible to query transformations based on the abstraction level of input and output models.

Table 5: Qualitative criteria for evaluating the reusability quality attribute

Domain	Criteria
Model Transformation	The ability to define modular model transformations
	The ease of defining modular model transformations
	The ability to use model transformations across different metamodels
	The ease of using model transformations across different metamodels
	The ability to tailor model transformations to a specific metamodel
	The ease of tailoring model transformations to a specific metamodel
	The ability to compose and create the chain of model transformations
	The ease of composing and chaining model transformations
	The ability to search model transformations
	The ease of searching model transformations
	The accuracy of the search results
	The ability to reuse existing model transformations
	The ease of reusing existing model transformations
Tools & Modeling Approaches	The ability to reuse existing models
	The ease of reusing existing models
	The accuracy of the reused models in the new context
	The ability to reuse existing metamodels
	The ease of reusing existing metamodels
	The ability to discover artifacts created through collaboration during different phases
	The ease of discovering artifacts created through collaboration during different phases
	The ability to describe and retrieve the model specifications
	The ease of describing and retrieving the model specifications
The accuracy of the retrieved specification	
MDE Process	The ability to reuse existing MDD processes
	The ease of reusing existing MDD processes
	The accuracy of the reused MDD processes in the new context

The modularity of transformation rules is one of the evaluation metrics that measures how easily these rules can be decomposed or merged and is closely related to the quality attributes of flexibility, ease of change, and reusability (Panahandeh et al., 2021). The following formula can be used to quantify this metric (Chavarriaga et al., 2014): $m=1-(d/r)$. Here, the d value represents the number of dependencies (implicit or explicit) between transformation rules, and r represents

the number of transformation rules in the transformation design model (TDM) (Chavarriaga et al., 2014).

1.4. Answer to RQ4

By reviewing existing works (Akiki & Maalouf, 2021; Alam et al., 2018; Franzago et al., 2018; D. Kolovos et al., 2013), we have identified a set of requirements and features that facilitate the collaboration and interaction of the teams during the modeling process. We have also identified qualitative and quantitative criteria and metrics for evaluating this quality attribute. Table 6 and Table 7 outline these requirements and criteria.

Table 6: Requirements and features that facilitate collaboration

Requirements & Features	Details
Support for multi-user environment with online or offline collaboration capability	The platform should support a multi-user environment with online or offline collaboration capability.
Providing an infrastructure for managing models throughout their lifecycle	The platform should provide an infrastructure for managing models throughout their lifecycle.
Providing a repository for storing models and related metadata	The platform should provide a repository for storing models and related metadata.
Providing modeling tools for creating, editing, and deleting models	The platform should provide modeling tools for creating, editing, and deleting models.
Ability to share models in different formats	The platform should have the ability to share models in different formats.
Support for a version control system	It should be possible to store artifacts in different versions.
	It should be possible to record and update the history of changes.
	It should be possible to search among different versions of artifacts.
Support for model merging	The platform should be able to merge the models.
Support for conflict management	It should be possible to synchronize and publish changes of models as a result of team collaboration.
	It should be possible to manage the conflict created in the model due to simultaneous editing.
	It should provide facilities for resolving conflicts
	It should be possible to highlight the selected element in the model by one of the stakeholders when modeling online.
	It should be possible to lock elements and highlight the locked element by other stakeholders.
	It should be possible to assign colors to each user when modeling online.
Support for visualization of models	It should be possible to illustrate the changes applied to the models in the editor during online modeling.
	It should be possible to display the mouse pointer of other stakeholders when modeling online.
Collecting information related to various aspects of the project	The platform should collect information related to various aspects of the project.
Support for a public notification service	The platform should support a public notification service and notify the model changes
Ability to monitor the stakeholders' activities during online modeling	It should be possible to display the details of the updating operation.
	It should be possible to display the list of active stakeholders at the moment.
Ability to interact in a defined and traceable manner with the artifacts	It should be possible to find out who is doing what on which part of the artifact.
	It should be possible to track the topics raised in connection with the artifacts.
	It should be possible to share design decisions.
	It should be possible to communicate indirectly through sending documents, comments and explanations.

Table 7: Criteria for qualitative analysis of collaboration

Domain	Criteria
Tools & Modeling Approaches	The ability to collaborate in a multi-user environment
	The ease of online or offline collaboration in a multi-user environment
	The ability to manage models throughout their lifecycle
	The ease of managing models throughout their lifecycle
	The ability to store models and their corresponding metadata in a central repository
	The accuracy of the stored models
	The ability to manage and manipulate the models by the tool
	The ease of using modeling tools to manage and manipulate the models
	The ability to share models in different format
	The ease of sharing models
	The accuracy of the shared models
	The ability to manage different version of models
	The ease of managing artifacts in different version
	The ability to merge models
	The ease of merging models
	The accuracy of the merged models
	The ability to manage conflicts in a systematic manner
	The ease of managing conflicts
	The accuracy of the automatic conflict management
	The ability to visualize models
The ease of visualizing models	
The accuracy of the visualized models	
MDE Process	The ability to collect project information from different aspect
	The ability to notify model changes
	The ability to monitor activities during collaborative modeling
	The ease of monitoring activities
	The ability to trace model manipulation to the user interaction
The ease of interaction with models	

To effectively collaborate in the modeling process, it is crucial to track team members' participation and the changes that they have made to the models. CHECKSUM (Akiki & Maalouf, 2021) is a technique that enables the monitoring of collaborative modeling, tracking of changes, and maintenance of an immutable Changelog. The Changelog is used to measure the level of contribution, which can be evaluated from three perspectives: temporal, operational, and qualitative. The temporal perspective measures the time spent on various operations performed on the model. The operational perspective indicates the type of operation performed on the model, while the qualitative perspective assesses the user's opinion regarding the output of their work. To quantify the level of contribution, each dimension can be assigned a weight and score, and the overall contribution score can be calculated by combining them.

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